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Digital Humanities**

Mika Hämmäläinen & Khalid Alnajjar (eds.)

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Fusing Bidirectional Chain-of-Thought and Reward Mechanisms: A Method for Enhancing Question-Answering Capabilities of Large Language Models for Chinese Intangible Cultural Heritage

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Abstract

Intangible cultural heritage is a living fossil of history, carrying the historical memories and cultural genes of a nation or region. However, in the wave of global modernization, intangible cultural heritage is facing unprecedented challenges. Digital technology can provide strong support for the protection and innovative development of intangible cultural heritage. In recent years, with the rapid development of large language models, we can achieve the digitization and intellectualization of intangible cultural heritage by collecting and organizing vast amounts of related data. Furthermore, the question-answering capabilities of these large language models enable the intelligent dissemination and popularization of intangible cultural heritage knowledge. Nevertheless, in previous research on vertical domain models, simple Supervised Fine-Tuning technical means made it difficult for the model to master the in-depth knowledge of intangible cultural heritage. Especially in complex reasoning and knowledge question-answering tasks, the performance of the model was often limited. Therefore, enhancing the question-answering capabilities of large language models in the field of intangible cultural heritage has become crucial for the intelligent dissemination of its culture. In previous research on vertical domain models, simple Supervised Fine-Tuning technical means made it difficult for the model to master the in-depth knowledge of intangible cultural heritage. Especially in complex reasoning and knowledge question-answering tasks, the performance of the model was often limited. Therefore, enhancing the question-answering capabilities of large language models in the field of intangible cultural heritage has become crucial for the intelligent dissemination of its culture.

Chain-of-Thought (CoT) continuously verifies and optimizes the reasoning process, gradually enhancing the output quality of large language models, thereby achieving iterative improvement. Presently, most Chain-of-Thought prompts utilize forward reasoning methods, which start from known facts and gradually derive conclusions based on certain reasoning

rules. In contrast, backward reasoning is a process that begins with the desired conclusion or goal and works backward to identify the conditions or evidence that support that goal or conclusion.

Previous research has introduced reverse reasoning primarily for the purpose of verification to obtain the final answer. For instance, Jiang et al. incorporated reverse reasoning to validate candidate answers for mathematical problems and selected the final answer through majority voting. Yuan et al. integrated reverse reasoning with meta-cognitive mechanisms and cognitive preference management to improve reasoning accuracy and efficiency. Liu et al. proposed the bidirectional chaining method, Bi-Chainer, to overcome the limitations of existing unidirectional chaining methods for complex logical reasoning.

In order to alleviate these problems, we propose a method of integrating forward and reverse thinking chains and reward mechanisms based on the completed large language model in the field of intangible cultural heritage. This method can enable the large language model to not only conduct forward reasoning when thinking, but also prove the rationality of forward reasoning through reverse questions and reverse reasoning to improve the accuracy of the original questions. In addition, we introduce a reward mechanism during training. Optimize the decision-making process through structural evaluation and content evaluation with different weights to improve the output quality of the model.

For instance, "In which historical period did Chinese shadow puppetry originate?" Using forward reasoning, the answer is: "Shadow puppetry is a folk art that tells stories through the projection of silhouettes made from animal hides or cardboard. During the Western Han Dynasty, cultural exchanges between China and foreign regions were frequent. The Book of Han records a story from the reign of Emperor Wu of Han, where a sorcerer used light projection to recreate the shadow of Consort Li. This is considered the prototype of shadow puppetry. Therefore, it originated in the Western Han Dynasty." If we employ reverse reasoning, starting from the conclusion that "the Western Han Dynasty is the origin period of shadow puppetry," we can ask the reverse question: "What made the Western Han Dynasty the origin period of shadow puppetry?" The answer would be: "During the reign of Emperor Wu of Han, a sorcerer used light projection to recreate the shadow of Consort Li, which is regarded as the prototype of shadow puppetry. This demonstrates that the Western Han Dynasty is the origin period of shadow puppetry." The answer aligns with the original question and its conclusion. Correct forward reasoning, reverse questions, and reverse reasoning will be rewarded based on keyword coverage and the size of the longest common sub-sequence. However, if under the original question, forward reasoning incorrectly predicts the answer as "Tang Dynasty", then subsequent reasoning and the answer will conflict, and no reward will be given, and the question-answering need to be re-evaluated and thought. This approach enhances the ICH-Qwen model's ability to solve inverse problems and perform inverse reasoning, and helps identify potential errors, thereby improving the accuracy and interpretability of answers to original questions.

We will conduct comparative experiments on the intangible cultural heritage question-

answering dataset with other thought chain methods (such as answer enhancement and question reorganization, etc.) to prove the advantages of our proposed method. At the same time, we also conducted ablation experiments to prove the effectiveness of each part, and we also migrated the method to other datasets to prove its domain adaptability.

This study aims to make a significant contribution to the protection, inheritance, dissemination, and innovation of intangible cultural heritage, while also providing new perspectives and methodologies for digital humanities and large language model technology research, ultimately promoting the sustainable development of intangible cultural heritage.

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Applying semantic change detection methods with contextualised word embeddings to discourse analysis

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This work aims to discuss the possibility of using transformers models to identify and analyse sites of 'semantic struggles' or contestations within political or media discourses. In practice, the goal is to extract 'controversial' terms, i.e. terms which are used most distinctively by different groups. Distinctive uses of keywords can be explained because they are utilised to grant greater or lower relevance to specific realities in sociopolitical debates, or because they acquire new meanings when they travel to new socio-cultural contexts. Therefore, the aim is to leverage transformers to understand the ways in which the meaning of words changes relative to the group that uses them.

This study builds upon previous works where static embeddings were created to investigate the discourse issued by the EZLN, a contemporary Maya social movement based in Chiapas, Mexico (Gribomont, 2023; Gribomont, *in press*). This movement claimed to offer a renovation of Marxist terminology because the 'old words had become so worn out that they had become harmful for those that used them' (Holloway, 1998, 180).

By extracting words which were used most distinctively by the EZLN in comparison with a corpus composed of discourses issued by other past and present Latin American left-wing insurgent groups, the affirmation could be assessed and areas of ideological ruptures between the EZLN and other organisations were uncovered. For instance, it was found that the word 'revolution' was used significantly differently by the EZLN in comparison to the other movements represented in the corpus. Hypothetically, this semantic difference can be explained by the Mexican historical context. The PRI (Revolutionary Institutional Party), a right-wing party which has been in power from 1929 to 2000, co-opted the 1910 Mexican revolution and aimed to institutionalise its principles in a new state model. This institutionalisation process of the Mexican revolution tainted or altered the meaning of the word 'revolution' in Mexico. It rendered the word unusable for the EZLN, which defines itself in opposition to institutional politics. This interpretation was confirmed via close reading.

These results were obtained by modelling all discourses together and adding context-specific tokens to target words so that distinct representations would be learned by a word2vec model (see Dubossarsky et al., 2019). For the present study, these experiments were reproduced with contextualised embeddings so as to allow for more granular interpretations. Notably, contextualised embeddings would allow for the assessment of the stability of word meanings within one (sub-)corpus. It would be possible to examine whether the semantic difference observed leads to a 'shrinking', 'expansion' or 'translation' of the meaning/connotation of words under investigation. For instance, we could verify the hypothesis that the high semantic difference between the word revolution in the EZLN and the reference corpus is due to a strong reduction of the semantics of the word.

However, the results obtained with word2vec were not reproducible with a BERT model. Neither the semantic distances observed for a single word across movements, nor the semantic distances observed between different words within the same movement could be observed when encoding our corpus with BERT. The hypothesis of the meaning of the word 'revolution' reducing in scope in the EZLN corpus could not be confirmed either when calculating the dispersion of the vectors for the token 'revolution' across different movements. The semantic differences generally appeared to be inconsequential and unstable, contrary to what had been observed with word2vec.

In the context of relevant scholarship on NLP and lexical semantic change (Boholm et al., 2024; Boholm & Sayeed, 2023; Cassotti et al., 2023; S'a, Silveira & Pruski 2024; Giulianelli, Del Tredici, & Fernández, 2020; Periti & Tahmasebi, 2024), this paper discusses various attempts at obtaining meaningful representations for such a task with BERT models, e.g. continuing to train the model with our data and fine tuning the models for classification, hoping it will help the model to better distinguish between different context-dependent uses of the same words. It also discusses the possibility of using siamese models which focus on similarity learning and might be better suited for this task.

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Names of Thrones: How LLMs Rank Names, Race, and Gender in Status Hierarchies

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Imagine a five-year-old about to enter a classroom for the first time. Even before stepping inside, their teachers, classmates, and automatic grading systems may already have subconscious expectations about their intelligence and future success--based on their first and last names. Across cultures, names tell a lot about their bearers as they carry deep personal, historical, and cultural significance and serve as a fundamental form of human expression (Bodenhorn and Bruck, 2006). They are connected to our deepest sense of self, signifying meaning and identity. Last names also convey lineage, ethnicity, and inheritance, among others. Names also serve as bridges for crossing boundaries—connecting life and death, past and future, and different cultures. They can transcend ethnic and cultural divisions, as seen in the common practice of adopting Western first names in America and Hong Kong (Li, 1997). Although Mill (1843) defined names as “meaningless markers” that tell us nothing certain about the identity of the named persons, names have been found to serve as powerful signals of gender, race, and status in the social hierarchy—a pecking order in which individual positions shape others’ expectations on their perceived competence and worth (Podolny, 2005;

Ridgeway, 2019). With the rapid and ubiquitous adoption of NLP tools and given that names are often an input for LLMs, it is crucial to recognize how LLMs may unfairly sort people into status positions and discriminate based on first and last names. While prior work has primarily investigated biases in first names (Bertrand and Mullainathan, 2004; Maudslay et al., 2019; An et al., 2024), little attention has been paid to last names and even less to the combined effects of first and last names.

In this study, we conduct a large-scale analysis with bootstrapping of 45,000 name variations across 5 ethnicities to examine how AI-generated responses exhibit systemic name biases in competence, wage, and leadership potential, particularly against non-Western names. One key contribution of our work is the disaggregation of Asian identities, a population projected to be the largest immigrant group in the U.S. by 2055. Unlike prior studies that treat Asians as a monolithic group, we distinguish among East, South, and Southeast Asians and find stark distinctions: while East and South Asian names tend to receive the highest AI rankings, Southeast Asian names face significant disadvantages, consistently scoring lowest in the three forms of inequality—below White, East Asian, South Asian, and Hispanic names. White names are predicted to score 3% lower academically than East Asian names, while Southeast Asian names are expected to score 9% lower. American students with White and East Asian names are projected to earn 12% and 14% more than those with Southeast Asian names, respectively. Our findings also reveal that, after controlling for other factors, LLMs tend to perceive longer names more favorably, suggesting an implicit association between name length and, perhaps, historical social status. Gender moderates biases in complex ways; LLMs assign girls higher predicted academic scores than boys in school but not in national competitions, while lowering the girls' wages in all racial groups. Additionally, spanning cultural categories by adopting Western first names improves AI-perceived status for East and Southeast Asian students, particularly for girls, suggesting how NLP systems inherit dominant

cultural preferences and reward assimilation for certain populations in their evaluations.

Our findings underscore the importance of intersectional and more nuanced understandings of race, gender, and mixed identities in the age of NLP, rather than relying on broad, monolithic, and mutually exclusive racial or gender categories. LLMs do not merely reflect societal biases; they actively construct new social hierarchies, institutionalize them, and shape long-term social and economic trajectories. Although names are often seen as a seemingly innocuous input for LLMs, name-based bias in LLMs influences how teachers assess student works, how employers screen candidates, how individuals perceive their peers, and how institutions distribute opportunities. Algorithmic reinforcement may perpetuate lasting disparities in humanity by making it increasingly difficult for individuals assigned lower status to escape their predicted paths. Meanwhile, those placed at the top of the hierarchy may face undue pressure as they are held to unfairly high expectations to excel and risk having their individual achievements reduced to racial stereotypes. To mitigate these harms for all, we propose algorithmic anonymization, removing name-based inferences from AI-driven evaluations, alongside fairness-aware interventions. We urge NLP researchers to go beyond merely “hiding” bias and discrimination and instead develop models that promote fairness to ensure that NLP systems do not become gatekeepers and amplifiers of human inequality and cultural hierarchies.

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LitAuthorDemoDB: An Open-Source Database of Literary Authors for Demographic Analysis

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Introduction

We present LitAuthorDemoDB, an open-source dataset of classic and contemporary authors with corresponding demographic information including gender, race/ethnicity, and nationality. While author datasets such as the Gale Books and Authors database and ISBNdb exist, they are not easily or freely accessible. Indeed, there is no direct download of datasets or API access to easily match an author to demographic information.

LitAuthorDemoDB is meant to provide readers and researchers an accessible, open-source, and community-updated and reviewed repository for author demographics. It is available for download at <https://github.com/IBM/LitAuthorDemoDB>. We plan to continually update with new authors and fields, particularly to increase the diversity of the dataset.

Creation

The first version of the database was created by prompting generative models to generate author and title pairs with various instructions such as recommending fiction, classic, Western literary canon, and global literary canon books. The models used were GPT 4o, Gemini 1.5 Pro, Llama 3.3 70B-Instruct, and Llama 3.1 8B-Instruct. We annotated each author with gender, race/ethnicity, and nationality by leveraging Wikipedia, author biographies on their official pages, and interviews.

Statistics

Currently, the dataset contains a total of 1,345 authors and 2,238 corresponding titles. Author demographics currently include gender, race/ethnicity, and nationality. A notes column is included with clarifications and extra information.

The current dataset is majority male (58%) with 41% female authors and 11 non-binary authors. It also contains a majority of White authors (78%). Meanwhile, 8% of authors are Asian, 8% are Black, and 3% are Latino. At least one, but less than 1% of authors are of the following racial and ethnic categories: Native American, Pacific Islander, and Aboriginal Australian. While the authors represent seventy-nine nationalities, about half of the authors are American and 20% are British. All other nationalities account for less than 5% of the dataset.

Revisions and Updates

The next version of the dataset will draw from a variety of genres as well as other sources such as WikiData with a focus on increasing gender, racial, and national diversity. Users will also be able to suggest corrections and new authors.

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